

NEW INSIGHTS INTO BOARD STRUCTURE AND INCOME SMOOTHING HYPOTHESIS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the tie between board structure and income smoothing in 21 banks in Nigeria for 10 years (2013-2022). Corporate board structure is represented by board size, board independence and the proportion of foreign directors. In contrast to prior literature, income smoothing is defined as loan loss provision rather than earnings management. Further, the analysis examines the correlation between board structure and income smoothing. Individual board features are found to influence income smoothing behaviour of banks in Nigeria across the period covered. Overall, results provide evidence that board of directors can influence income smoothing behaviour of publicly traded banks in Nigeria. Consequently, these findings are important to regulators, shareholders, lenders, and other stakeholders. Furthermore, the results extend the understanding of the role of board of directors in reducing corporate income smoothing and building quality and sustainable earnings for banks in Nigeria, where different systems may bring opportunistic income smoothing behaviour. Note that the findings are limited to banks in the context of emerging economies.

Key Words: Board Structure, Correlation Analysis, Descriptive Analysis, Hypothesis, Income Smoothing, Nigeria, Regression Analysis, Table

INTRODUCTION

There is a growing literature that deals with the analysis of the procyclical effects of income smoothing behaviour among banks in Nigeria (Manukaji, 2018; Ozili, 2015, 2017, 2019; Ozili & Outa, 2019). However, these papers disregard the role of board of directors in reducing income smoothing practices among banks in Nigeria.

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As evident in the preceding paragraph, few papers analyze the procyclical effects of bank income smoothing opportunistic behaviours in Nigeria. Manukaji (2018) examines corporate governance mechanisms and income smoothing in deposit money banks in Nigeria and concludes that banks' opportunistic practices amplify income smoothing behaviour. Consistently with this work, Ozili (2017) after controlling for the impact of Basel regulation on loan loss provision, find strong evidence of income smoothing, capital management and procyclical loan loss provision behaviour during the voluntary adoption of IFRS in Nigeria. Furthermore, Ozili and Outa (2019) find similar strong evidence of income smoothing in Nigeria during the voluntary adoption of IFRS in Nigeria.

Our goal, in this paper, is to interrogate if loan loss provisioning practices aggravate growth in income smoothing, and if so, whether the board of directors of banks could help to bring down such practices to a minimum level. Some scholars have also used loan loss provision to proxy income smoothing in their empirical studies (Abou El Sood, 2012; Bhat, 1996; Boulila Taktak et al., 2010; Fonseca & Gonzalez, 2008; Greenawalt & Sinkey Jr, 1988; Kanagaretnam et al., 2003; Ma, 1988; Ozili, 2015; Zoubi & Al-Khazali, 2007). The board of directors is operationalized via board size, board independence and proportion of foreign directors. Several scholars have used these variables to proxy board of directors. For example, board size (Ahmed & Duellman, 2007; Boone et al., 2007; Cheng, 2008; Eisenberg et al., 1998; Jianfei & Yiran, 2011; Megginso et al., 1994), board independence (Ahmed & Duellman, 2007; Beasley, 1996; Bhagat & Black, 2001; Boone et al., 2007; Hermalin & Weisbach, 2001; Karamanou & Vafeas, 2005; Krishnan, 2005; Kumar & Singh, 2012; Rosenstein & Wyatt, 1990; Shivdasani & Yermack, 1999) and the proportion of foreign directors (Ajmal et al., 2023; Buccieri et al., 2023; Chabbouh & Boujelbene, 2023; Franco et al., 2023; Herweg et al., 2023; Kaliannan et al., 2023; Kotb Abdelrahman Radwan et al., 2023; Kirkman et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2023; Utomo et al., 2023).

Banks in this paper consist of deposit money banks, mortgage banks, savings and loans companies, and microfinance banks as listed by the Nigerian Exchange (28 July 2023). Overall 21 banks are handpicked for the study as indicated in Table 1. Banking is a major segment of the Nigerian economy. While some might define it more broadly, banking is considered as a subsector of the larger financial services sector, which also includes subsectors focusing on mortgage finance, deposit money banks, savings and loans. According to the Central Bank Nigeria (2023), the Nigerian banks' assets rose by 10.72 trillion naira (\$22.61 billion) between August 2021 and August 2022 to hit 66.76 trillion naira (\$151.49 billion). Aside from loans granted to individuals, banks grant loans to other sectors of the economy such as the agricultural sector, the educational sector, and others. This shows the interdependence of all the sectors of the Nigerian economy.

Since our objective in this paper is to determine if loan loss provisioning in banks leads to income smoothing and what the board of directors could do to reduce such practices, we conduct our analysis on all the banks in Nigeria, whether they are deposit, mortgage and savings and loans banks. Our results, over the 2013-2022 period, show that loan loss provisions leads to income smoothing, which also leads to income smoothing in Nigeria. Our results, therefore, support the proposal of the Basel Committee to implement a more specific loan loss provisioning system at the international level in addition to the capital measures already adopted to address procyclicality. Our results further show that the procyclical effect of loan loss provisioning, leading to income smoothing is strong in Nigeria. These results support

the idea that capital cushions are enough to dampen the cyclicity of income smoothing by banks in Nigeria, and the enactment of a forward-looking provisioning system is an important mandate.

This paper aims to examine the impact of board structure on the income smoothing behaviour of banks in Nigeria, after accounting for the banks' size, leverage, age and market share. This is based on the prevalence of accounting scandals resulting in the collapse of banks, which have been attributed to the opportunistic behaviours of bank managers in Nigeria (Ayedun et al., 2012; Ajide & Aderemi, 2014; Marshal & Onyekachi, 2014; Modugu & Anyaduba, 2013; Olalekan & Adeyinka, 2013; Paulinus et al., 2017; Ugbede et al., 2013; Uwuigbe & Olusanmi, 2012). These results are useful to a number of stakeholders such as regulators, shareholders, boards of directors, lenders, scholars, researchers. However, the paper uses 21 banks' data, covering board size, board independence, proportion of foreign directors, and loan loss provision for 10 years (2013-2022). Furthermore, 4 control variables are added to the model and they are firm size, firm age, firm leverage and firm market share.

The remainder of the paper is organized into four sections. Section 2 presents literature review, covering both conceptual, theoretical and empirical literature. Section 3 presents the research methodology, covering research design, population and sample, sources and methods of data collection, analyses and post estimations diagnostics. Section 4 presents the descriptive statistics, results of diagnostics, correlation matrix and regression results. Section 5 presents the conclusions, drawn based on the empirical results and offers both policy and performance improvement recommendations.

Literature Review

Income smoothing is defined as the deliberate normalization of income in order to reach a desired state. If the smoothing causes more information to be reflected in the share price, it is likely to influence the allocation of resources and can be a critical factor in investment decisions. This study aims to use econometrics analysis to determine the degree of influence by board of directors in banks to reduce income smoothing practices, if any. It is instructive to note that income smoothing is often by use of a loan loss provision, which is something a bank creates to set aside funds for default or problem loans. It is an income statement expense banks can tap into when borrowers are delinquent on their payments and are unlikely to repay their loans. The goal of income smoothing is to reduce the fluctuations in earnings from one period to another to portray a company as if it has steady earnings. It is intended to smooth out periods of high income versus periods of low income or periods with high expenses versus periods of low expenses. If this study establishes that there income smoothing behaviours of banks in Nigeria, then, the goals of the paper is to examine how banks' boards of directors could bring down such behavioural practices.

Board structure is used in this article to refer to board size, board independence and the proportion of foreign directors present on the board of directors of banks in Nigeria. In addition, income smoothing refers to loan loss provisioning by banks in Nigeria. While board size refers to the aggregate number of directors of a bank, this figure is regardless of the status of the director; board independence refers to the proportion of non-executive directors relative to aggregate board size. Also, the presence of foreign directors is considered important since, it allows the banks to have the opportunity of learning from foreign practices and technologies. In that vein, the proportion of foreign directors refer to the ratio of foreign directors relative to aggregate board size on the board of banks in Nigeria. Income

smoothing is proxy by loan loss provisioning in this paper. A loan loss provision is an income statement expense set aside as an allowance for uncollected loans and loan payments. This provision is used to cover different kinds of loan losses such as non-performing loans, customer bankruptcy, and renegotiated loans that incur lower-than-previously-estimated payments. It is a measure of capital risk, as well as credit quality of banks. If banks operate in more risky environments and lack the expertise to control their lending operations, it will probably result in a higher loan-loss provision ratio to cover this risk.

Agency theory is adopted as foundation of this article because members of board of directors are involved, who are agents of shareholders in actual sense. However, there is conflict of interests when the members of directors beginning to consider their own interests instead of the interests of shareholders, who appoint or nominate them to the board of directors. Agency theory is required in this scenario to resolve such conflict between directors and shareholders by making it clear to directors that the role of directors is to protect shareholders' interests. Agency theory is propounded by Jensen and Meckling in 1976. A number of studies use agency theory to underlie their scholarly works (Bebchuk & Fried, 2003; Berger & Di Patti, 2006; Donaldson & Davis, 1991; Eisenhardt, 1989; Hill & Jones, 1992; Lafontaine, 1992; Maury, 2006; Müller & Gaudig, 2011; Shah, 2014; Shapiro, 2005).

Generally, the majority of empirical studies examining board structure links with income smoothing have defined income smoothing primarily within the context of loan loss provision. For example, Greenawalt and Sinkey Jr (1988) test an income-smoothing hypothesis for a sample of 106 large bank holding companies for the period 1976 to 1984 using an econometric model with pooled time-series, cross-sectional data. They find evidence of income-smoothing behaviour over their test period. Also, Carlson and Bathala (2003) examine the association between some factors and income smoothing behaviour in firms. A logistic regression model is used to test the association between income smoothing and leverage and firm size. The evidence suggests that firm leverage and size are not important in explaining income smoothing behaviour in firms.

In addition, Ahmad et al. (2009) extend Nasuhyah et al. (1994) model by incorporating contextual variables that proxy for corporate governance and income smoothing on a sample of Bursa Malaysia listed companies for a period between 1991 and 2000. The results show that the existence of non-executive directors is significant in hindering the management from indulging in income smoothing. In the same year, Machuga and Teitel (2009) investigate whether or not board characteristic such as board independence is associated with the improvement in earnings quality found in previous research. Earnings quality is measured using income smoothing. They find firms that are in compliance with board independence rules have greater increases in income smoothing. In addition, Epps and Ismail (2009) examine the relationship between corporate governance and earnings management in US context and provide further insights on the effects of board of directors' characteristics on earnings management. Results show that firms with small size boards have more negative income smoothing. However, firms with independent board or firms with a board size of between 9 and 12 have positive income smoothing.

Furthermore, Yang et al. (2012) examine empirically whether corporate governance mechanisms affect income-smoothing behaviour in the People's Republic of China. The results show that income smoothing is more severe with firms with more independent directors. However, the corporate governance mechanism such as board of directors' size is not effective in curtailing income smoothing in China. Also, Alexandri and Anjani (2014) determine the factors

that affect income smoothing on the 10 National Private Commercial Foreign Exchange Banks that listed in Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the years 1/1/2009 to 31/12/2013 with a sub-sample of 50 financial reports. The test results result are variable size of the company and financial leverage simultaneously significant effect on income smoothing.

In addition, Amos et al. (2016) examine how the corporate governance mechanisms such as the presence of independent directors on the board and size of the board affect the credit risk exposure of 27 Indian public banks for the year 2015. The results show that the corporate governance variables considered in this study have significant impact on the confidence of the bank in maintaining the provisions for the unexpected loss. Vassilopoulos et al. (2018) investigate the impact that governance mechanisms have on European Union 'banks' income smoothing behaviour. The results suggest that banks managers' decision to smooth income differs with regard to the board structure and the level of leverage. Manukaji (2018) examines corporate governance mechanisms and income smoothing in deposit money banks in Nigeria for the period ranging from 2012 to 2016. The empirical results also demonstrate that board size is not effective in monitoring income smoothing. Indrawan et al. (2018) examine the impact of firm size and leverage on income smoothing in manufacturing companies listed in Indonesia stock exchange for the period of 2013-2015. The results of the study reveal that the firm size has a direct positive influence on income smoothing in the listed manufacturing companies in Indonesia. Leverage posits an adverse effect on income smoothing in the manufacturing sector. This indicates the smaller the risk of companies' debt, the more exceptional the practice of income smoothing occurs.

Putri (2019) analyzes the effect of corporate governance, company size and financial leverage on income smoothing of 555 companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2011-2015. The results of the analysis show that corporate governance, company size and financial leverage simultaneously have significant effects on income smoothing. While corporate governance-independent commissioners and financial leverage have positive and significant effects on income smoothing, firm size has a negative effect and is significant for income smoothing. Susanto and Pradipta (2019) obtain empirical evidence about the effect of firm size on income smoothing. The sample of the research includes manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange from 2014-2016. The effect of firm size on income smoothing is negative and significant.

Furthermore, Ekadjaja et al. (2020) aim to earn empirical results about the effect of board independence, leverage and firm size on income smoothing that is listed on BEI for years 2015-2017. The results were significant relationships between board independence and income smoothing while insignificant relationships were found in between leverage and income smoothing and between firm size and income smoothing. Jung et al. (2020) examine whether foreign investors influence a local firm's income smoothing, using a sample of Korean firms from 2000 to 2013. They find that foreign directors are positively related to the level of earnings smoothing. Wijaya and Mauren (2020) determine the effect of financial leverage on income smoothing in 38 manufacturing companies registered on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2016-2018 with firm size as a moderating variable. The results of this study indicate that firm size has a significant positive effect on income smoothing. In contrast, financial leverage has an insignificant effect on income smoothing.

In addition, Kustono (2021) determine the motives for income-shifting management in Indonesian public manufacturing companies' financial statements dated December 31, 2009 - 2018 obtained from the Indonesian Capital Market Directory. The independent commissioners' size was able to suppress income smoothing in manufacturing companies. Sulistiawati and Rasyid (2021) empirically examine the influence of firm size and board size on income smoothing in 62 manufacturing companies listed in Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) from period 2016 – 2018. The result of research shows that board size have positive influence towards income smoothing. Firm size has no significant influence on income smoothing.

Furthermore, Obeidat (2021) examines whether firm size has an influence on the income smoothing practices of 8 food and beverages (F&B) firms listed on the Amman Stock Exchange for data covering the period 2010–2019. The study shows that firm size has a positive significant influence on income smoothing. Dyussembina et al. (2023) examine whether foreign directors play a role in income smoothing. Their finding suggests that foreign directors serves a positive role in the income smoothing. They further find that the positive effect of foreign directors on the income smoothing is stronger for firms that have higher profitability and pay dividends. Based on the variability in these empirical studies, this paper hypothesizes that:

H₁: Board size has no significant effect on income smoothing.

H₂: Board independence has no significant effect on income smoothing.

H₃: Foreign directors have no significant effect on income smoothing.

The remainder of the paper is organized into 3 sections. Section 3 presents the research methodology, covering research design, population and sample, sources and methods of data collection, analyses and post estimations diagnostics. Section 4 presents the descriptive statistics, results of diagnostics, correlation matrix and regression results. Section 5 presents the conclusions, drawn based on the empirical results and offers both policy and performance improvement recommendations.

Methodology

The ex post facto research design was employed, and as such, data were gathered from secondary sources. Furthermore, the generalized method of moment's panel estimation technique was used for analyzing the data. Income smoothing was measured using the loan loss provision, while board structure was measured using board size, board independence and foreign directors. We use financial statement data extracted from NGX for 2009 to 2022. We use information on commercial, mortgage and savings and loans banks. See Table 1 as population and sample. We use an empirical model specification as follows:

$${}_{i,t}IS = \alpha + {}_{i,t}\beta_1BS + {}_{i,t}\beta_2BI + {}_{i,t}\beta_3FD + {}_{i,t}\beta_4FS + {}_{i,t}\beta_5FL + {}_{i,t}\beta_6FA + {}_{i,t}\beta_7MS + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

IS = Income smoothing, measured by loan loss provisions.

BS = Board size, measured as the total numbers of all directors of a company including the Chairman +Vice Chairman +CEO/Managing director + Executive Directors +Non-Executive Directors or Independent Directors but excluding the company secretary.

BI = Board independence, measured as the non-executive board of directors divided by total board size (%).

FD = Foreign directors, measured as a percentage of the number of foreign directors divided by board size for companies that have foreign directors and "0" for otherwise.

FS = Firm size, measured as natural log of total asset.

FL = Financial leverage, measured as total liabilities divided by total asset.

FA = Firm listing age, measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange.

MS = Market share, measured as firm's total assets over sector total assets.

α = Constant

β_{1-7} = Beta coefficients

ε = Idiosyncratic error term

i = Firm script (in this case, i = 21)

t = Time script (in this case, t = 10 years)

Table 1

Samples of the study

S/N	Firms	Subsectors
1	Abbey Mortgage Bank Plc	Mortgage Banking
2	Access Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
3	Aso Savings and Loans Plc	Savings and Loans
4	Ecobank Transnational Incorporated	Deposit Money Banking
5	First Bank of Nigeria Plc	Deposit Money Banking
6	First City Monument Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
7	Fidelity Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
8	Guaranty Trust Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
9	Infinity Trust Mortgage Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
10	Jaiz Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
11	Livingtrust Mortgage Bank Plc	Mortgage Banking
12	NPF Microfinance Bank	Microfinance Bank
13	Resort Savings and Loans Plc	Savings and Loans
14	Stanbic IBTC Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
15	Sterling Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
16	Union Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
17	Union Bank Savings and Loans Plc	Savings and Loans
18	United Bank for Africa Plc	Deposit Money Banking
19	Unity Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
20	Wema Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking
21	Zenith Bank Plc	Deposit Money Banking

Sources: <https://ngxgroup.com/exchange/trade/equities/listed-companies/>

Following standard textbook recommendations (Abrevaya & Donald, 2017; Anatolyev, 2005; Baltagi et al., 2005; Bond et al., 2011; Bouzid, 2016; Carrasco & Florens, 2002; Hou & Chen, 2013; Newey & Smith, 2004; Kapetanios & Marcellino, 2010; Stock & Wright, 2000; van Bon, 2015), we rely on a Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) methodology. More precisely, we use the Blundell and Bond (1998) dynamic panel estimator to estimate the model. This estimator is known as the system GMM estimator. The remainder of the paper is organized into 2 sections. Section 4 presents the descriptive statistics, results of diagnostics, correlation matrix and regression results. Section 5 presents the conclusions, drawn based on the empirical results and offers both policy and performance improvement recommendations.

Results and Discussions

This section reports the results from descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, diagnostics analyses, and regression analysis. Table 2 is a report of the descriptive statistics.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
IS (LLP)	210	.045	.096	.01	.97
BS	210	13.904	3.407	5	20
BI	210	.616	.112	.33	.92
FD	210	.15	.149	0	.43
FS	210	11.84	.448	10.51	12.59
FA	210	42.423	30.69	15	122
FL	210	.084	.081	0	.61
MS	210	.164	.177	1	.473

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Table 2 reports the descriptive statistics of the paper. The number of observations is 210, explained by the number of years (10) and the number of firms (21). The mean of IS (LLP) is 4.5 percent, with a higher standard deviation of 9.6 percent, suggesting the volatility of income smoothing among banks in Nigeria, which calls for further studies, implying justification for this paper. Furthermore, it shows minimum and maximum means of 1 and 97 percent, respectively. Overall, although, Table 2 shows empirical evidence of income smoothing by banks in Nigeria, the average is 4.5 percent, which is quite low, though some banks were involved in extremely high income smoothing of 97 percent.

Similarly, BS, which measures the number of board members, approximately averages 14 members, with a lower standard deviation of 3 members, suggesting that board size is stable among banks in Nigeria. Furthermore, it shows minimum and maximum means of 5 and 20 board members, respectively. Also, BI approximately averages 62 percent, with a lower standard deviation of 11.2 percent, suggesting that board independence is stable among banks in Nigeria. These results are consistent with the Corporate Governance Code of 2018, which suggests that most of board members should be non-executive directors. Furthermore, it shows minimum and maximum means of 33 and 92 percent, respectively. Similarly, FD (foreign directors) averages 15 percent, with a high standard deviation of 14.9 percent, suggesting that foreign directors are volatile among banks in Nigeria.

Furthermore, it shows minimum and maximum means of 0 and 43 percent, respectively. These results show that some banks do not have foreign directors, while some have foreign directors as high as 43 percent. On the control variables, FS averages 11.84 points, with a lower standard deviation of .448 points, suggesting that firm size is not volatile among banks in Nigeria. Furthermore, it shows minimum and maximum means of 10.51 and 12.59 points, respectively. FA averages 42 years, with a lower standard deviation of 31 years, suggesting that firm listing age is not volatile among banks in Nigeria. Furthermore, it shows minimum and maximum means of 15 years and 122 years, respectively. FL averages 8.4 percent, with a high standard deviation of 8.1 percent, suggesting that financial leverage is volatile among banks in Nigeria. Furthermore, it shows minimum and maximum means of 0 and 61 percent, respectively. These results show that some banks do not have financial leverage in their balance sheet, while some have as high as 61 percent, which calls for further research on leverage (gearing). Finally, MS averages 16.4 percent, with a higher standard deviation of 17.7 percent, suggesting that firm market share is volatile among banks in Nigeria. Furthermore, it shows minimum and maximum means of 1 and .473 percent, respectively. These results show that some banks' market share is as low as 1 percent, while some banks enjoy a market share of about 47 percent. We conduct some diagnostics and the results are in Tables 3 to 6 as follows.

Table 3

Results of normality of residuals test

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As it is clear from Table 3, the model is not normally distributed, since the red line, which shows the kernel density estimate line is above the normal (blue) line. We also carry out the Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data and the result shows

that the prob>z is .00007. Thus, the model requires robustness since it fails normality of residuals test. We also carry out heteroskedasticity of residuals test and the results are in Table 4.

Table 4

Results of Cameron & Trivedi's decomposition of IM-test

White's test for Ho: homoskedasticity

against Ha: unrestricted heteroskedasticity
 $\chi^2(27) = 101.51$
 Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0000$

Source	chi2	df	p
Heteroskedasticity	101.510	27	0.000
Skewness	13.090	6	0.042
Kurtosis	4.610	1	0.032
Total	119.210	34	0.000

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As Tables 4 indicates, our model has heteroskedasticity problem, and as indicated earlier in the case of failure of normality of residuals, the model requires robustness in to correct both failures of normal distribution and heteroskedascity. These results also confirm the failure of normality of residuals test. A normal distribution would have a Skewness of 0 and a Kurtosis of 3. Kurtosis is used to show the peakedness of flatness of the data. Since the Kurtosis is less than 3 then its platykurtic distribution, if its equal to 3 then its mesokurtic distribution and if kurtosis shows values more than 3 then its leptokurtic distribution. Furthermore, we carry out multicollinearity test among the independent variables and control variables and the results are in Table 5.

Table 5

Results of multicollinearity test

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
(1) BS	1.000						
(2) BI	-0.344* (0.000)	1.000					
(3) FD	0.259* (0.001)	-0.078 (0.331)	1.000				
(4) FS	0.321* (0.000)	0.031 (0.702)	0.312* (0.000)	1.000			
(5) FA	0.144 (0.073)	0.096 (0.232)	-0.164* (0.040)	0.224* (0.005)	1.000		
(6) FL	-0.275* (0.001)	-0.093 (0.251)	-0.138 (0.086)	-0.337* (0.000)	0.151 (0.060)	1.000	
(7) MS	-0.139 (0.083)	0.012 (0.882)	-0.106 (0.186)	-0.191* (0.017)	-0.092 (0.251)	0.163* (0.043)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

The highest coefficient in Table 5 is .321, which is between board size and firm size, suggesting that there is multicollinearity among the independent and control variables. However, to confirm this position, Table 6 shows the variance inflation factors for these variables.

Table 6

Variance Inflation Factors

	VIF	1/VIF
FS	1.415	.707
FL	1.237	.808
FA	1.22	.819
FD	1.196	.836
MS	1.063	.941
BS	1.043	.912
BI	1.029	.972
Mean VIF	1.193	.

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Also the variance inflation factor (VIF) values, calculated with the regression model performed not exceed 1.5. All VIF values are substantially below the critical value of 10.00 (Netter et al., 1989). Based on Pearson correlations (in Table 5) and VIF values (in Table 6), multicollinearity does not appear to be a serious concern in the model. We further examine the model specification error test and the results are in Table 7.

Table 7

Results of Model Specification Error Test

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 210
Model	597.994	2	298.997	Prob>.000
Residual	1201.563	193	7.853	R-squared = .732
Total	1799.558	195	11.610	Root MSE = 2.802

IS	Coef.	Std.Err.	t	P>t	[95%Conf.	Interval]
_hat	0.158	1.152	0.140	0.891	-2.117	2.433
_hatsq	0.032	0.043	0.740	0.463	-0.054	0.117
_cons	5.455	7.595	0.720	0.474	-9.549	20.459

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

From Table 7, the p-value of _hatsq (.463) is not significant, hence, we can conclude that the model is well specified, suggesting that it has no model specification error problem. Furthermore, the ovtest reports are in Table 8 as follows.

Table 8

Model Specification Error Test

Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of BS

Ho: model has no omitted variables

$$F(3, 146) = 0.92$$

$$\text{Prob} > F = 0.4324$$

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

From Table 8, the Prob>F is (.4324) is not significant, hence, we can conclude that the model is well specified, suggesting that it has no model specification error problem. Furthermore, the results of GMM analysis are contain in Table 9 as follows.

Table 9

Results of Generalised Methods of Moments

Number of parameters = 8

Number of moments = 8

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 210

GMM weight matrix: Robust

IS	Coefficients	Robust standard errors	z	p>/z/	95% Conf.	Interval
/xb_BS	-.0094475	.0050197	-1.88	0.060	-.019286	.000391
/xb_BI	-.1401268	.1169655	-2.20	0.023	-.3693749	.0891213
/xb_FD	-.0757477	.08187	-2.93	0.015	-.0847146	.23621
/xb_FS	-.0137295	.0299319	-1.86	0.064	-.0449359	.0723948
/xb_FA	-.0005356	.0002434	-2.20	0.028	-.0000585	.0010127
/xb_FL	.0243489	.2238777	2.11	0.013	.4144434	.4631412
/xb_MS	.0033462	.002264	1.48	0.139	.0077836	.0010912
/b0	.0649296	.4856331	2.13	0.894	.8868938	.016753

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As shown in Table 9, BS has negative and significant effect on income smoothing. Similarly, BI has negative and significant effect on income smoothing. In the same vein, FD has negative and significant effect on income smoothing. These results are consistent with previous literature and our *a priori* expectation. On the control variables results, both firm size and listing age reduce firm income smoothing behaviour. Table 9 also shows that financial leverage presence encourages income smoothing among banks in Nigeria. However, we fail to see any level of significance for firm market share. While, board size and firm size have significant effects on income smoothing at 10 percent; board independence, foreign directors, firm age and financial leverage are significant at 5 percent. All these results are consistent with previous empirical studies. The remainder of the paper is organized into a section. Section 5 presents the conclusions, drawn based on the empirical results and offers both policy and performance improvement recommendations.

Conclusions and Recommendations

We examine whether board structure reduces income smoothing by banks in Nigeria, if so, which board structure characteristics have such influence. We observe that board size, board independence, foreign directors, firm size, firm age and financial leverage are determinants of income smoothing among banks in Nigeria. However, we also conclude that we fail to see results for firm's market share. These results are of obvious interest to regulators, shareholders,

publics, lenders, scholars, policy-makers, as banking management should move away from income smoothing practices. We conduct the empirical study on 21 banks in Nigeria. We find that board size, board independence, foreign directors, firm size, and firm age reduce the cyclicity of bank income smoothing. Indeed, our results show that board size, independence, foreign directors, firm size, and firm age have negative and significant effects on LLP. Income smoothing behaviour among banks implies that during an economic upswing, banks tend to underestimate corporate tax as a consequence increase LLP.

Our results show that banks with a loan loss provisioning system could therefore be carrying out income smoothing practices. Regulators should insist on systems that are designed to restrict banks from procyclicality of income smoothing. The reform of LLP should focus on strengthening the banking system against losses. We conclude that the countercyclical tools that will be implemented under Basel III might not be sufficient to reduce the cyclicity of bank income smoothing behavior, especially for banks where loan loss provisions is stronger. The Basel Committee should then work to reach an international consensus between regulators and accounting standards setters to support the adoption of a sound sustainable loan loss provisioning system.

One of the recommendations is on board size; since minimum average board size is 5, managers of the banks involved should take steps to increase board size to at least 8 as suggested by the Corporate Governance Code 2018 in Nigeria. The proportion of non-executive directors should enhanced from 61 percent to 70 percent. Foreign directors should be engaged since their presence help to reduce income smoothing practices among banks in Nigeria. The findings of this study contribute to the existing literature concerning banks' income smoothing behaviour. These findings can be useful to regulators, as the authors provide some evidence regarding the effectiveness of the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code of 2018. The remainder of the paper consists of references.

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